

WATERPROOFNESS AND ADHESION OF BITUMINOUS MASTIC

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Abstract. *This article deeply analyzes the results of water resistance and adhesion strength of the developed waterproof material. It is revealed that under low water pressure conditions, the results of determining the water resistance of bitumen mastic samples are given. Also, the developed bitumen mastic samples were tested to determine the strength properties, adhesion to the base of the waterproof material in accordance with GOST 26589-94. The developed composite waterproof material No. 5 successfully passed the test, since no signs of swelling were found on the surface of the sample.*

Keywords: *bitumen mastic, waterproof material, pyrolysis distillate, corrosion protection, erosion protection, water resistance, adhesion strength.*

Introduction. Today, a number of scientific studies are being conducted in the world to create a new generation of waterproof materials used in the construction of buildings and structures based on bitumen compositions with high performance and improving properties. In particular, special attention is paid to determining the methods for obtaining waterproof materials based on a composition of local raw materials and waste from the oil and gas industry, determining the physical, mechanical and technological properties of waterproof material obtained from secondary raw materials, and developing a technology for obtaining composite waterproof material [1-4].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific research has been conducted on the creation and application of technology for obtaining new effective bitumen compositions with improved technological, physical, mechanical and operational properties based on waste from the local oil and gas, chemical and oil and fat industries, and certain results have been achieved.

The new development strategy of Uzbekistan defines the tasks of “Wide introduction of innovations in the economy, development of cooperative ties between industrial enterprises and scientific institutions” [5].

In this regard, it is important to conduct scientific and practical research on the development of technology for producing composite waterproof materials from bitumen and pyrolysis distillate.

Research methods. 1) Water resistance tests. This test method is applicable to materials that will be used in low water pressure conditions, such as in the upper and lower layers of roofing cladding or vapor barrier layers, according to GOST EN 1928-2011 [6]. During the test, the sample is exposed to a water pressure of no more than 60 kPa for 24 hours.

The device used, described in detail in Figure 1, includes a cylindrical metal chamber with a flange and an internal diameter of 150 mm. It is equipped with an open-ended tube for air removal and is connected to a water vessel located at a height of at least 1 meter from the chamber.

This design allows for careful pressure control and ensures uniform load distribution on the material being tested, which is critical for assessing its water resistance and other properties relevant at low water pressure.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the device for determining water resistance at low pressures

1 - lower rubber sealing gasket; 2 - specimen placed face down to water; 3 - laboratory filter paper; 4 - indicator mixture for detecting traces of water penetration, uniformly applied to the filter paper, for example a mixture of white powdered sugar (99.5%) and methylene blue dye (0.5%), sifted through a sieve with a mesh size of 0.074 mm and dried in a desiccator over calcium chloride; 5 - laboratory filter paper; 6 - a round viewing window made of ordinary window glass, 5 mm thick at a pressure of <math>< 10</math> kPa, 8 mm thick at a pressure of 60 kPa; 7 - upper rubber sealing gasket; 8 - steel ring clamp; 9 - wing nut; 10 - air outlet valve; 11 - water inlet valve; 12 - valve for supplying and removing water; 13 - vessel with water for creating and maintaining pressure up to 60 kPa (pressure is regulated by the height of the vessel with water).

Testing methodology. To test the material using the described device, the sample is installed in it so that its front side faces the water. Then, the wing nuts 9 on the ring clamp are carefully tightened to ensure tightness. After this, the valve 11 is opened, allowing water to fill the chamber. It is important to leave the valve 10 open for air removal. As soon as the chamber is completely filled with water, the valve for air removal 10 is closed.

The water pressure is then adjusted to the specification or specification applicable to the materials being tested. The sample is held at this pressure for 24 ± 1 hours. After this time, the sample is carefully inspected for any changes in the color of the top sheet of filter paper that may indicate water penetration or other important characteristics of the material.

2) Adhesion tests. To conduct the test, the sample is made up of two concrete tiles with a mastic layer applied to them, and they are glued together in a cross-shaped manner. The area of the glued section is $(30 \times 30) \pm 2$ mm. Preparation of the mastic for testing, as well as requirements for the surface treatment of concrete tiles and the technique of applying the mastic, including consumption per tile, application method, number of layers, conditions for the formation of intermediate and final layers, as well as the conditions for curing the finished sample, must be strictly defined in the regulatory documentation for a specific type of mastic.

Test procedure: The test procedure involves fixing the sample in the grips of the tensile testing machine using a special device. This is followed by checking the zero setting of the force measuring device, setting the specified speed of movement of the movable grip, and then activating the stretching mechanism. To process the test results, the adhesion strength to concrete (R_c) in megapascals (or kilograms-force per square centimeter) is calculated using a special formula. This measurement allows us to evaluate the efficiency and reliability of the adhesion of the mastic to

the concrete surface, which is a key indicator for determining the applicability of the mastic in specific construction contexts.

$$R=P/S$$

P - maximum breaking force, H (kgf);

S - bonding area, m² (cm²).

The result is rounded to 0.01 MPa (0.1 kgf/cm²).

Research results and discussions. The methodology for assessing water resistance is used to analyze materials that are intended for use in low water pressure conditions. This includes such areas of application as the creation of upper and lower layers of roofing cladding or the installation of a vapor barrier layer, according to the GOST EN 1928-2011 standard [7].

Table 1

Results of determination of water resistance of bitumen mastic samples

Name of indicators	Experiments		
	1-layer	2-layer	3-layer
1-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -70%, Without fillers			
Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface
2-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Microcalcite-5%			
Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface
3-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Kaolin - 5%			
Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface
4-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Graphite -5%			
Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface
5-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Man-made waste of JSC “AGMK” - 5%			

Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface	There are no traces of water visible on the surface
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Within the framework of this method, samples are tested under a pressure not exceeding 60 kPa for 24 hours. In addition, the developed samples were tested to determine the strength properties, adhesion to the base of the waterproof material in accordance with GOST 26589-94 [8]. The results of these tests are presented in Table 2, which describes in detail the obtained data on the adhesion strength of waterproof materials to the base.

Table 2

Results of testing samples of bitumen mastic for strength properties of adhesion

Name of indicators	Experiments		
	1-layer	2- layer	3- layer
1-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -70%, Without fillers			
Adhesion strength, MPa with concrete	0,6	0,6	0,7
2-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Microcalcite-5%			
Adhesion strength, MPa with concrete	0,4	0,45	0,5
3-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Kaolin - 5%			
Adhesion strength, MPa with concrete	0,2	0,2	0,3
4-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Graphite -5%			
Adhesion strength, MPa with concrete	0,15	0,2	0,2
5-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Man-made waste of JSC “AGMK” - 5%			
Adhesion strength, MPa with concrete	0,1	0,1	0,2

The developed compositions of the samples are fixed in the grips of the tensile testing machine using a device, the zero setting of the force measuring device is checked, the specified speed of movement of the movable grip is set and the stretching mechanism is activated [9-11].

The adhesion strength to concrete (R_{sc} , kgf/cm²) is calculated using the formula:

$$R=P/S$$

where P - the maximum tensile strength, N (kgf);

S - the bonding area, m² (cm²).

The result is rounded to 0.01 MPa (0.1 kgf/cm²).

Fig. 2. Developed samples of bitumen mastic

Conclusion. The composite waterproofing material No. 5 developed by us successfully passed the test, as no signs of swelling were found on the surface of the sample. This indicates its high stability and efficiency in waterproofing conditions. This indicates that the material has the necessary characteristics for reliable waterproofing, is resistant to moisture and retains its properties under operating conditions.

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